

Awareness Levels and Participation of Beneficiaries of Asmita Yojana in Palghar District of Maharashtra: An Application of Diffusion of Innovation Theory

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Abstract: This study will examine the awareness levels and participation of beneficiaries of Asmita Yojana in Palghar district of Maharashtra. Asmita Yojana, launched in 2018 is aimed towards providing young girls and women good quality sanitary pads at a subsidised rate. The sanitary napkins being made available at a subsidised rate to girls and young women of ZP schools is an innovation. The study will measure the levels of awareness and participation of the end beneficiaries of the said scheme. The study involves application of the diffusion of innovation theory. Data is collected through a structured questionnaire from a random sample of the population in the geographical region of Palghar. The data analysis is done using regression analysis and one sample T test.

Keywords: Asmita Yojana, Diffusion of innovation, health communication, participation, availing benefits.

Introduction

The diffusion of the new product, innovation or idea can be propagated through the various channels of communication. However, all individuals and social groups do not have the same access to this information. Fraser and Restrepo (1998) opine that communication inequalities, are the differences in exposure to public health communication messages and capacity to access, process, and act upon the information received, are influenced by social determinants and may result in disparities in health-related knowledge, behaviour choices, and, ultimately, health outcome. This makes for a case of study of health messaging, government schemes and public policy and their adoption or use amongst the beneficiaries. It is pertinent to measure the levels of public

awareness and investigate the diffusion of innovation that has taken place in the process of implementation of Asmita Yojana in Palghar region of Maharashtra. Asmita Yojana is aimed towards empowering young girls and women by providing them good quality sanitary pads at a subsidised rate. The innovation is making the sanitary napkins available at a subsidised rate to girls and young women of ZP schools. The newspaper coverage of the scheme also throws some insights into the scheme. The reports from the year 2018 onwards. According to the Loksatta newspaper, there is a need to take a closer look into the lack of public awareness communication lapse in the implementation of the Yojana. The Hindu newspaper reports that the Asmita Yojana's aim was to get young girls and women use hygienic products but ironical that the villagers don't seem to be aware of the scheme. An earlier report in The Hindu also mentions that women from Palghar district are yet to benefit and avail from the scheme but the claims made by the officials are on the contrary. A news report in the Indian Express also talks about improving the quality of the napkins but there doesn't seem to be any initiative on the public official's part to communicate the same to the people. Thus the researcher found it interesting to conduct field research and unearth more findings.

Review of literature

The review of literature raised important questions regarding the public being aware of such yojanas, the role of communication plays in the implementation of such schemes in India. Li (2005) mentions lot of the schemes get bureaucratized and too centralised in their techniques. He says the concept of governmentality focuses on population and their empowerment. But it must be judged by its yield, it provokes us to ask how particular government programs are devised, the techniques they assemble. Communication thus plays an indispensable role in the delivery and manifestation of health goals. Moseley (2004) puts forth that a new product or innovation, in order for it to be adopted by the targeted social group or the potential beneficiaries, it must be communicated to them effectively otherwise it might not be understood and eventually accepted by them. According to Healthy People 2010 guidelines, health communication includes the research on and implementation of communication strategies to inform and influence individual and community decisions that enhance health. Health communication can lead to conditions of disease prevention & promotion of better health. Research shows that effective communication can lead to an improvement in interpersonal and group interactions. Health related public service announcements have traditionally been made on hoardings, radio, television & print such as pamphlets & newspapers. Campaigns have also been done through community based programs. Schiavo (2013) articulates the meaning of communication strategies specifically related to health as a statement describing the overall approach used to accomplish communication objectives. It is thus

very timely, imperative & important to check the process of dissemination itself, whether it has translated into the practice and eventually benefited the targeted beneficiaries. In the area of communication studies the innovations are conceptualized as new information or ideas. The spread of this information or news happens through either mass media or interpersonal communication. Research can measure the speed and direction of the message's transmission and the effect of changing key variables such as the language of message, the communication channel (spoken, written, etc.), and the nature of exposure (Rogers and Kincaid 1981). In health promotion and its communication, innovations are defined as good ideas for healthy behaviours and lifestyles. The diffusion and spread of such innovations amongst the targeted groups coincides with development and empowerment of communities.

Objectives of the Study

In India, Health Communication has not proven to be effective in influencing individuals and the community. Health Communication that seeks to influence and engage about menstrual health isn't socially accepted yet and is often not talked about. Politicians and bureaucrats still believe that different economical and infrastructural projects under taken by the government is enough to eradicate poverty. In this context, diffusion studies can greatly help in gauging the dissemination and implementation of public policy or a government scheme. Talking about government policies as innovations, mass media channels as well as interpersonal communication can play a pivotal role in disseminating the same. Policy diffusion studies reflect that a government scheme's faster adoption by the beneficiaries or the social group depends upon both the factors.

- To find out the level of the awareness of innovation amongst the beneficiaries.
- To examine the extent of participation of the beneficiaries in the scheme.
- To find out whether the beneficiaries are able to avail the benefits of the scheme.

Conceptual framework

Research Methodology

The methodology is quantitative in nature. The sample is from the geographic region of Palghar. Random sampling was done from the zilla Parishad schools of Palghar district. Girl students aged from 11-19 years who are beneficiaries of the Asmita Yojana and studying in Zilla Parishad Schools in Palghar were included.

Hypotheses of the study

- The diffusion of innovation is dependent upon the awareness of the innovation
- The participation of the beneficiaries causes higher diffusion of innovation.

Statistical Techniques Used

Data was analysed using Multiple Regressions Analysis method and One Sample T test. Correlation analysis is a statistical tool used to measure the strength and direction of relationship between two variables. The hypotheses were tested for establishing the relationships between the Diffusion of Innovation (Dependent variable) and the three factors that determine its success (Independent variables). This test is used to analyze the gap between the observed value on adoption of the innovation and comparison value. The sample data is compared with tested values for level of significance for each of the questions. The one sample T test shows that there is a significant difference in the sample mean and the test mean. This has been concluded by calculating the significance value i.e., if the level of significance < 0.05 then we accept the alternate hypothesis to prove that a significant difference exists in the sample mean and the tested mean.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

1. Diffusion of Innovation and Awareness of innovation

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.614a	.377	.372	.955

a. Predictors: (Constant), How aware are you of the process under the scheme Asmita Yojana? (AWARENESS OF INNOVATION)

2. Diffusion of Innovation and Availing of benefits

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.572 ^a	.328	.321	.992

a. Predictors: (Constant), How regularly do you avail the benefits of the scheme? (AVAILING THE BENEFITS)

3. Diffusion of Innovation and Participation of the beneficiaries

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.705 ^a	.498	.493	.858

a. Predictors: (Constant), How often do you share the information regarding the scheme with others? (PARTICIPATION)

One Sample T- Test: This test is used to analyse the gap between the observed value on adoption of the innovation and comparison value.

	One-Sample Test						
	Test Value = 0					95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Lower	Upper	
How aware are you of the process under the scheme Asmita Yojana? (AWARENESS)	32.164	108	.000	3.587	3.37	3.81	
How easy/difficult is to avail the benefits of the scheme? (AWARENESS)	29.113	108	.000	3.394	3.16	3.63	

How regularly do you use the sanitary napkins availed through the scheme? (AVAILING THE BENEFITS)	33.204	108	.000	1.578	1.48	1.67
How regularly do you use the sanitary napkins availed through the scheme? (AVAILING THE BENEFITS)	33.204	108	.000	1.578	1.48	1.67
Do you convey to the teachers/headmasters/parents the quality of the napkins availed through the scheme? (PARTICIPATION)	27.694	108	.000	3.009	2.79	3.22
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Findings

Regression analysis is used to predict the value of a variable based on the value of another variable. The variable the study wants to predict is called the dependent variable. To find out the same, Collinearity Statistics was conducted. It helped in understanding the relationship between Diffusion of Innovation and Awareness of Innovation. The above model summary tables provide the R value. The R value represents the simple correlation and is 0.555 (the "R" Column), which indicates a 55.5 % high degree of correlation. The one sample T test shows that there is a significant difference in the sample mean and the test mean. This has been concluded by calculating the significance value i.e., if the level of significance < 0.05 then we accept the alternate hypothesis to prove that a significant difference exists in the sample mean and the tested mean.

Conclusion

It is thus clearly evident from the data analysis that the diffusion of innovation is dependent upon the awareness of the innovation and the participation of the beneficiaries causes higher diffusion of innovation. The process of diffusion involves spreading or dissemination of information, innovation or an idea to the members of a social group. The

purpose of diffusion of innovation is the adoption of that innovation, idea or product by the potential beneficiaries. The process of adoption of new innovation or product goes through five steps of decision making, viz. knowledge or information about the innovation itself, forming an attitude towards the innovation, accepting or rejecting the innovation, implementation of the innovation and lastly confirmation of the innovation or the product. Schiavo (2013) contends that the intended beneficiaries must participate and be involved in the strategizing process because there is direct proportionality between the participation of the communities and their influencers and success of communication efforts and eventually attaining those objectives. Engaging communities and different sectors is often accomplished in health communication practice by working together with organizations and leaders who represent them or by directly involving members of a specific community at the outset. The product or innovation as stated earlier is not the sanitary napkin itself but its availability through an app named the Asmita app at subsidised rates through the Self-Help Groups or the SHGs. As a new product or innovation, in order for it to be adopted by the targeted social group or the potential beneficiaries, it must be communicated to them effectively otherwise it might not be understood and accepted by them.

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